

Simple estimation of snow density in an Alpine region

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ABSTRACT

Study region: The Upper Adige catchment, South Tyrol, Italy.

Study focus: The empirical snow density models of Jonas et al. (2009) and Sturm et al. (2010), are compared with a simple equation that predicts snow density based on the day of the year only.

New hydrological insights: The simple equation presents similar uncertainty compared to the more complex empirical models. It appears robust for regions with snow of Alpine and Maritime characteristics, and can be easily recalibrated as more data become available. The proposed model estimates snowpack density as an initial value of 200 kg/m³ at the beginning of the snow cover season (November 1st), to be increased by 1 kg/m³ for each elapsed day. The model residuals standard deviation is about 13%, which is comparable to the within-site spatial variability.

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1. Introduction

Mountains are of fundamental importance for the supply of water worldwide (e.g. [Viviroli et al., 2007](#)), and their snowpack is often a very relevant component of water storage. Estimating snow water equivalent (SWE) is therefore essential in water resources management. SWE at a site is the product of snow depth and snow density. Depth is a relatively simple quantity to measure, while density requires more complex and costly procedures ([Jonas et al., 2009](#); [Egli et al., 2009](#)). As an alternative to direct measurements, models can be used for estimation. Many snow density models used in practice require as input at least temperature and precipitation information, while less demanding models would be desirable to convert the increasingly available mass of snow depth data from several direct and indirect techniques into hydrologically more useful SWE ([McCreight and Small, 2014](#)).

[Jonas et al. \(2009\)](#) propose an empirical model for Switzerland, consisting of linear regression equations predicting snow density from snow depth, differentiated by elevation and season, and to be corrected by an offset specific for each region within the country. The authors find that the model yields errors comparable with the spatial variability of snow density at a site, in the order of 10–20%. On a similar line, [Sturm et al. \(2010\)](#), propose a model that predicts density based on depth and the day of the year, with parameters that depend on regional climatic conditions. [McCreight and Small \(2014\)](#), point out that both the [Jonas et al. \(2009\)](#) (J09), model and the [Sturm et al. \(2010\)](#) (S10) model embed the assumption of a positive correlation between snow density and depth, which in reality only holds in space at a given time, or at appropriate time scales ([McCreight and Small, 2014](#)), and cannot be applied for density estimates at daily step. Indeed, the authors of the J09 model clearly warn that their model should not be applied for converting time series of snow depth into series of snow water equivalents. Based on this consideration, [McCreight and Small \(2014\)](#), propose a more sophisticated model including

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Table 1

Sturm et al.'s snow density model suggested default parameters (see Sturm et al., 2010, for additional details).

Region type	ρ_{max} (kg/m ³)	ρ_0 (kg/m ³)	k_1 (cm ⁻¹)	k_2
Alpine	597.5	223.7	0.0012	0.0038
Maritime	597.9	257.8	0.001	0.0038
Prairie	594.0	233.2	0.0016	0.0031
Tundra	363.0	242.5	0.0029	0.0049
Taiga	217.0	217.0	0	0

Fig. 1. Location of the snow depth measurement stations (of which details are provided in Table 3).

snow depth anomalies, which can be applied at daily steps when density measurements are available for calibration within distances of tens of kilometers from the point of estimation. They find that both J09 and S10 models show an inferior performance when applied at daily step; however, they suggest that these simpler models could be applied whenever direct density measurements are not available.

This contribution compares snow density estimated by the S10 and J09 models using measured snow depth, with a simple model relating density to the day of the year. Based on the results, indications for snow density estimations are proposed for situations where no (or only a few and sparse) measurements are available.

2. Materials and methods

The S10 model predicts snow density as:

$$\rho = (\rho_{max} - \rho_0)(1 - \exp(-k_1h - k_2DOY)) + \rho_0 \quad (1)$$

where h is snow depth (cm), DOY is a counter of the day of the year (set to 1 on January 1st, with October 1st being -92 to account for the winter season extending across two years in the northern hemisphere). The other terms in equation (1) are parameters for which the authors suggest default values for different snow types according to Sturm et al. (1995) (see Table 1 for details).

Table 2

Jonas et al.'s snow density model parameters (see Jonas et al., 2009, for additional details).

DOY	$\rho^0(\text{DOY}, Z)$ (kg/m ³)			K(DOY, Z) (m ⁻¹)		
	Z > 2000 m asl	Z > 1400 m asl and Z < 2000 m asl	Z < 1400 m asl	Z > 2000 m asl	Z > 1400 m asl and Z < 2000 m asl	Z < 1400 m asl
–61: –31	206	183	149	47	35	37
–31: 0	203	190	201	52	47	26
1: 31	206	208	235	52	47	31
32: 59	217	218	279	46	52	9
60: 91	272	281	333	26	31	3
92: 121	331	354	347	9	15	25
122: 153	378	409	413	21	29	19

Table 3

Characteristics of the available snow depth measurement stations in South Tyrol. Station codes are plotted for reference in Fig. 1.

Name	Code	Elevation (m asl)	Measurement start date
Roia di Fuori	0059	1833	20/12/1981
Melago	0109	1915	23/12/1981
Malga Lazaun-Senales	1539	2450	02/01/1985
Plan	2058	1620	18/12/1981
Waidmannalm-Avelengo	2396	2040	04/01/1986
Fontana Bianca-Ultimo	2439	1890	19/12/1981
Casere	5019	1590	01/12/1994
Predoi	5049	1449	20/12/1981
Monte Chiusetta-Cadipetra	5159	1590	26/12/1981
Riva di Tures	5449	1600	21/12/1981
Diga di Neves	5529	1860	02/11/1988
Piz la Ila	6171	1995	20/12/1981
Monte Cuzzo-Maranza	6769	2010	23/12/1981
Ciampinoi	7339	2150	15/12/1985
S. Floriano	7850	1872	20/12/1981
Pennes	8019	1487	18/12/1981

The J09 model describes density as a function of depth, with an intercept ρ_0 and a slope K grouped by month and elevation range, and can be written as:

$$\rho = \rho_0(\text{DOY}, Z) + K(\text{DOY}, Z)h \quad (2)$$

where $\rho_0(\text{DOY}, Z)$ is the model intercept and $K(\text{DOY}, Z)$ is the model slope; both are not a continuous function of DOY but assume a constant value for ranges of DOY corresponding to the different months. It should be noted that the J09 model is acknowledged by the authors to not be suitable for daily step applications. When this model is applied to time series, in fact, the monthly variation of model coefficients yields discontinuities at the end of each month, that should be corrected e.g. by interpolation.

The S10 and J09 models were applied at 16 monitoring stations managed by the Autonomous Province of Bolzano, in the Italian Alps at the border with Austria (Fig. 1 and Table 3) where snow depth measurements were made available. The time series that were retrieved for this exercise end in autumn 2010, while the stations continue to operate on a regular basis. The parameters of both models should be in principle calibrated with available data (as done by McCreight and Small (2014) for the J09 model). However, in this contribution we examine their applicability in the absence of calibration.

For each station, snow density was computed using measured depth with:

- the S10 model with all the “Alpine” and “Maritime” types of snow (Sturm et al., 1995), using the corresponding parameter combinations shown in Table 1;
- the J09 model with the parameters derived by the Authors for different altitudinal zones in the Swiss Alps (Table 2), excluding the regional offset suggested by the authors (this offset is in the order of 10 kg/m³ and is therefore negligible in our context).

For comparison with the S10 and J09 models, we consider a set of sparse snowpack bulk density measurements for winters 2008–09, 2009–10 and 2010–11 made available from the Autonomous Province of Bolzano. These measurements come from specific campaigns conducted by the Province with a bi-weekly frequency. The measurements are taken in “snow fields” near weather stations between 1000 and 2500 m a.s.l., not necessarily corresponding to snow depth measurement stations, using a simple vertical core tube method with on-site dynamometric weight determination (data reported in Table 4). The “snow fields” correspond to open grassland with slope below 10°, in order to minimize the aerodynamic effects of obstacles and vegetation as well as creep of the snow pack, following the procedures outlined in Cagnati (2003). Measurements are not repeated at the same sites during each campaign and, consequently, have an unsystematic character. Therefore they could not be used to validate the density model at specific sites or as time series.

Fig. 2. Measured snow density (regression equation shown) and regression model residuals. The ST model is the polished form of the regression equation.

However, plotting all the measured snow densities together in time shows a clear trend, that can be fairly described by a linear relationship (Fig. 2, above), although densities in the spring tend to grow faster than earlier in winter. The residuals of the linear model are reasonably uniform (Fig. 2, below) although they display a weak parabolic trend similar to what highlighted by McCreight and Small (2014), with reference to S10 and J09 models. The residuals standard deviation is 13%, similar to what Jonas et al. (2009), report for the J09 model and Sturm et al. (2010), report for the S10 model. The linear regression model equation, can be written as:

$$\rho = \rho_0 + K(DOY + 61) \quad (3)$$

with coefficients that can be written as $\rho_0 = 200\text{kg/m}^3$ and $K = 1\text{ kg/m}^3$ per day. We denote this equation as the “South Tyrol (ST) model”. Equation (Sturm et al., 2010) only applies up to about $DOY = 150$ (end of May). In the following, we compare the performance of the S10 and J09 models applied to the time series of snow depth at the 16 monitoring stations, with the one of the ST model.

Fig. 3. Comparison of ST with S10 model predictions.

3. Results

We plot the density estimated with the S10 model using the Alpine and Maritime snow type model parameters (see Table 1), as a function of the one with the ST model (Fig. 3), by considering all points corresponding to the time series of snow depth in all 16 measurement stations. The S10 model is always reasonably close to the ST model, with a slight tendency to underestimation with Alpine snow parameters, and overestimation with Maritime snow parameters. The relationship between ST and S10 models is not linear, though, S10 returning lower densities in the low and high ends of the density range.

We repeat the exercise with the J09 model (Fig. 4). In this case, we apply the J09 model to daily steps without modifications, hence accepting that the monthly-changing model parameters cause a “jumpy” behavior of snow density. Corrections to remove this behavior (e.g. McCreight and Small, 2014) do not affect the model characteristics of interest in this work. The

Table 4Manual snow density measurements considered in this study. Elevations are derived from SRTM digital elevation data: <http://srtm.csi.cgiar.org>.

Site code	Earliest measurement date	Latest measurement date	n. of measurements	Lon	Lat	Elevation m asl
10FR	02/10/2010	3/24/2011	14	10.50	46.57	2229
12FO	03/03/2010	3/24/2010	2	11.21	45.92	1346
13PR	3/31/2010	3/31/2010	1	11.58	46.34	1668
14PO	2/24/2010	2/24/2010	1	11.69	46.43	1369
15TR	12/23/2009	3/24/2010	4	11.69	45.84	163
16PT	11/11/2009	3/31/2010	4	11.66	46.12	1629
16ZH	1/13/2010	04/07/2011	23	10.68	46.48	2260
17LA	1/14/2010	3/23/2011	14	10.76	46.75	2428
18SB	4/14/2010	4/14/2010	1	11.79	46.20	1605
19PF	2/24/2010	4/14/2010	5	11.16	45.76	1140
1PEI	3/24/2010	3/24/2010	1	10.66	46.37	2032
21MB	04/09/2010	04/09/2010	1	10.52	46.05	1765
22CI	3/24/2010	3/31/2010	2	11.77	46.45	2114
22GR	04/09/2009	04/08/2011	8	11.10	46.79	2016
26SP	04/07/2010	4/14/2010	2	11.80	46.39	2001
27KL	3/18/2009	3/16/2011	6	11.27	46.69	1989
28FB	02/10/2010	4/21/2011	13	10.83	46.49	1900
29FL	3/24/2010	3/24/2010	1	10.85	46.29	1876
29GP	2/25/2009	03/10/2011	15	11.11	46.53	1546
30PN	05/07/2010	5/26/2010	4	10.58	46.23	2705
31LD	2/18/2010	04/07/2011	17	11.37	46.93	1958
34JH	04/01/2009	4/21/2011	18	11.33	46.84	1975
35VC	3/31/2010	04/05/2010	2	11.76	46.26	1910
52PV	12/02/2010	3/31/2011	8	11.90	46.56	1992
5PSV	2/24/2010	03/03/2010	2	11.90	46.56	1992
61KT	12/01/2010	03/09/2011	6	11.71	46.68	2052
64SJ	12/02/2010	04/08/2011	8	11.77	46.52	2017
71UH	2/17/2010	3/16/2011	2	11.47	46.60	1846
8PAN	3/23/2010	3/23/2010	1	11.75	46.31	1558
Alm1Proveis	11/28/2010	11/28/2010	1	11.04	46.50	1719
Alm2	11/28/2010	11/28/2010	1	11.04	46.51	1840
bP1A	2/25/2011	2/25/2011	1	11.04	46.51	1860
bP1B	2/25/2011	2/25/2011	1	11.04	46.51	1878
bP1C	2/25/2011	2/25/2011	1	11.04	46.51	1878
P1A/B	3/29/2011	3/29/2011	1	11.03	46.51	2085
P1C	3/29/2011	3/29/2011	1	11.03	46.51	2090
P2A	3/29/2011	3/29/2011	1	11.04	46.51	1879
P2B	3/29/2011	3/29/2011	1	11.04	46.51	1879
P3A	2/25/2011	2/25/2011	1	11.03	46.49	1461
PA2	2/25/2011	2/25/2011	1	11.03	46.51	2128
PB2	2/25/2011	2/25/2011	1	11.03	46.51	2103
Proveis1	4/27/2010	4/27/2010	1	11.04	45.50	211
Proveis2	4/27/2010	4/27/2010	1	11.04	46.51	1860
R7GZ	12/02/2010	3/16/2011	6	11.69	46.85	2083

J09 model systematically estimates snow density lower than the ST model. The difference decreases if we apply parameters for lower elevation (<1400 m asl) snow, compared to the case of high elevation snow.

4. Discussion and conclusions

From this comparison of S10 and J09 models with the linear trend of existing snow density measurements in South Tyrol, we first of all observe that both the S10 model with Alpine snow parameters and the J09 model based on snow data from Switzerland underestimate density relative to the ST model, suggesting that the region may tend to Maritime snow type characteristics. The J09 model seems to capture snow characteristics closer to those of South Tyrol only when using parameters for lower elevation sites in the Swiss Alps. Based on these considerations, we may argue that, when snow density measurements are not available to calibrate the S10 and J09 models on a daily basis, using these equations with default parameters such as those of Tables 1 and 2 may not yield significant benefits compared to a model relating density only to the day of the year, achieving a residuals standard deviation of about 13% in the case of South Tyrol. The difference among the three models is anyway small, and the Ockham's razor principle suggests that the simplest model should be preferred in the absence of contrary evidence. As density is a very conservative value, typically bounded between 0.2 and 0.4, reasonable estimates are somehow expected also from very simple models especially for regional scale water resources assessment. Nevertheless, when studying snow with specific characteristics or regions with higher snow variability compared to South Tyrol, more complex models may be needed.

The average snow density of a day in the year (that McCreight and Small (2014), call "density climatology") follows a clearer trend along the year compared to single-day snow density. Mizukami and Perica (2008), derive simple models of

Fig. 4. Comparison of ST with J09 model predictions.

density climatology differentiating four regional clusters in the western US, and show that factors such as elevation and distance to a large water body are the main variables explaining the spatial variability of density climatology. They also point out that the variability of density from year to year is sufficiently small to justify an estimation of climatologies with relatively short records. The equation fitted to sparse snow density data available in South Tyrol, $\rho = 200 + (DOY + 61)$, is consistent with the density climatology models calibrated by Mizukami and Perica (2008), for predominantly Alpine or

Fig. 5. Comparison of the ST model (continuous line) with the upper and lower bounds of the models of Mizukami and Perica (2008) (dashed lines). Error bars represent the 13% residuals standard deviation of the ST model.

Maritime type snow in the western US (as shown in Fig. 5), suggesting that it can represent a reasonable first guess estimate when no specific density data are available, and applicable for screening-level estimation of density for Maritime or Alpine snow type in the boreal hemisphere. Otherwise, this approach may be simplistic for more specialized purposes, and should be applied with care.

Conflict of interest

I have no conflict of interest related to the content of this work.

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References

- Cagnati, A., 2003. *Strumenti di misura e metodi di osservazione nivometeorologici: manuale per i rilevatori dei servizi di previsione valanghe*. AINEVA, Trento, 133 pp.
- Egli, L., Jonas, T., Meister, R., 2009. Comparison of different automatic methods for estimating snow water equivalent. *Cold Regions Sci. Technol.* 57, 107–115.
- Jonas, T., Marty, C., Magnusson, J., 2009. Estimating the snow water equivalent from snow depth measurements in the swiss alps. *J. Hydrol.* 378, 161–167.
- McCreight, J.L., Small, E.E., 2014. Modeling bulk density and snow water equivalent using daily snow depth observations. *Cryosphere* 8, 521–536, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5194/tc-8-521-2014>.
- Mizukami, N., Perica, S., 2008. Spatio-temporal characteristics of snowpack density in the mountainous regions of western United States. *J. Hydrometeorol.* 9, 1416–1426, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1175/2008JHM981.1>.
- Sturm, M., Holmgren, J., Liston, G.E., 1995. A seasonal snow cover classification system for local to global applications. *J. Clim.* 8, 1261–1283.
- Sturm, Matthew, Taras, Brian, Liston, Glen E., Derksen, Chris, Jonas, Tobias, Lea, Jon, 2010. Estimating Snow Water Equivalent Using Snow Depth Data and Climate Classes. *J. Hydrometeorol.* 11, 1380–1394, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1175/2010JHM1202.1>.
- Viviroli, D., Dürr, H.H., Messerli, B., Meybeck, M., Weingartner, R., 2007. Mountains of the world, water towers for humanity: typology, mapping, and global significance. *Water Resour. Res.* 43, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1029/2006wr005653W07447>.